

ITERATIVE ALGORITHM FOR ESTIMATING THE ELEMENTS OF THE MATRIX GAIN OF A KALMAN FILTER

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Abstract. A stable iterative algorithm for estimating elements of the matrix gain of the Kalman filter has been developed. The traditional Kalman filter equations are given. Algorithms for autonomous calculation of the stationary Kalman filter gain are presented, which are performed under conditions relating to the system parameters. A non-linear iterative equation is solved for the gain of the Kalman filter. Modeling results are given, these Kalman filtering expressions for a linear discrete system and the actual filtering process is the current process for predicting and correcting recursive and iterative nature.

Keywords: dynamic object control systems, iterative algorithm, adaptive filtering, Kalman filter, estimation, covariance matrix, Kalman filter gain, modeling.

Аннотация. Разработан устойчивый итерационный алгоритм оценки элементов матричного коэффициента усиления фильтра Калмана. Приведены традиционные уравнения фильтра Калмана. Представлены алгоритмы автономного расчета стационарного коэффициента усиления фильтра Калмана, которые выполняются в условиях, связанных с параметрами системы. Решается нелинейное итерационное уравнение для коэффициента усиления фильтра Калмана. Приведены результаты моделирования, эти выражения фильтрации Калмана для линейной дискретной системы, а фактический процесс фильтрации является текущим процессом прогнозирования и коррекции рекурсивного и итеративного характера.

Ключевые слова: системы управления динамическими объектами, итерационный алгоритм, адаптивная фильтрация, фильтр Калмана, оценка, ковариационная матрица, коэффициент усиления фильтра Калмана, моделирование.

Аннотация. Калман филтрининг матрицали кучайтириши коэффициентларини баҳолаш учун турғун итератив алгоритм ишлаб чиқилган. Анъанавий Калман филтри тенгламалари берилган. Тизим параметрлари билан боғлиқ шароитларда бажариладиган стационар Калман филтри кучайтириши коэффициентини автоном ҳисоблаш алгоритмлари келтирилган. Калман филтри ҳисоблаш учун чизиқли бўлмаган итератив тенглама ечилган. Моделлаштириши натижалари берилган, чизиқли дискрет тизим учун ушбу Калман филтрлаш ифодалари ва ҳақиқий филтрлаш жараёни рекурсив ва итератив хусусиятини башорат қилиши ва тузатиши учун жорий жараёндир.

Калит сўзлар: объектни динамик бошқариши тизимлари, итератив алгоритм, адаптив филтрлаш, Калман филтри, баҳолаш, ковариацион матрица, Калман филтрининг кучайтириши коэффициентини, моделлаштириши.

The quality criterion is taken as the expectation of the cost function: it must be minimized using a sequence of controls. The procedure for choosing these controls, which is a multi-step decision-making process, is the problem of stochastic control. The main reason for the divergence in the Kalman filter is that the filter gain tends to zero very quickly. Therefore, the estimate ceases to be dependent on the sequence of observations and the growing error of observations does not affect it. [1-6]. Thus, the noted circumstances indicate the need to create stable algorithms for estimating the state of dynamic systems under parametric a priori uncertainty and to synthesize

computational schemes for their practical implementation [7-11]. Consider a linear dynamic system described by the equations

$$\begin{aligned} x_{i+1} &= Ax_i + w_i, \\ z_i &= Hx_i + v_i, \quad i \geq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where x_i is the n -dimensional state vector at time i , z_i is the m -dimensional measurement vector at time i , A is the $n \times n$ system transition matrix, H is the $m \times n$ output matrix, w_i is the plant noise at time i , and v_i is the measurement noise at time i . $\{w_i\}$ and $\{v_i\}$ are Gaussian zero-mean white random processes with covariance matrices Q and R , respectively.

To estimate the state vector x_i of the dynamic system (1), traditional Kalman filter equations of the form are usually used:

$$K_i = P_{i/i-1} H^T (H P_{i/i-1} H^T + R)^{-1}, \quad (2)$$

$$P_{i/i} = (I - K_i H) P_{i/i-1}, \quad (3)$$

$$P_{i+1/i} = Q + A P_{i/i} A^T, \quad (4)$$

where, for $i \geq 0$, with initial condition $P_{0/-1} = P_0$ for the time instant, where there are no measurements given, The Kalman filter gain K_i is a matrix of dimension $n \times m$, R and P_0 are positive definite matrices.

We present algorithms for the steady state Kalman filter gain autonomous computation. These algorithms hold under conditions concerning the system parameters.

We define the matrix

$$G_i = K_i H, \quad (5)$$

where G_i is a nonsymmetric matrix of dimension $n \times n$.

Information for us, it is also clear that there exists a steady state value

$$\tilde{G} = \tilde{K} H. \quad (6)$$

Also, we define the matrix

$$S = H^T R^{-1} H. \quad (7)$$

Note that S is an $n \times n$ symmetric positive semidefinite matrix and S is a positive definite if $\text{rank}(H)=n$; this means that S is a nonsingular matrix in the case, $\text{rank}(H)=n$ with $m>n$ [12].

Now, the Kalman direct steady state filter gain factors are calculated. We present algorithms for the direct computation of the steady state Kalman filter \tilde{K} . The proposed algorithms compute directly the steady state Kalman filter gain, that is, without using $\tilde{G} = \tilde{K} H$. All these algorithms hold under the assumption that $n=m$. Note that, since $\text{rank}(H) = n$, H and S are nonsingular matrices. On a basis (5) and (7), we are able to derive the following nonlinear iterative equation with respect to the Kalman filter gain K_k :

$$K_{k+1} = G_{k+1} H^{-1} = (Q A^{-T} H^T R^{-1} + A K_k) [H Q A^{-T} H^T R^{-1} + R H^{-T} A^{-T} H^T R^{-1} + H A K_k]^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

$$G_{i+1} = ((Q A^{-T} S) + (A) G_i) [(S^{-1} A^{-T} S + Q A^{-T} S) + (A) G_i]^{-1}.$$

Then, the nonsingularity of S and (7) allow us to write the equality in (8) as

$$\begin{aligned} K_{k+1} &= (Q A^{-T} H^T R^{-1} + A K_k) [H Q A^{-T} H^T R^{-1} + H S^{-1} A^{-T} H^T R^{-1} + H A K_k]^{-1} = \\ &= (C + D K_k) [L + B K_k]^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where

$$L = H Q A^{-T} H^T R^{-1} + H S^{-1} A^{-T} H^T R^{-1} = H(Q + S^{-1}) A^{-T} H^T R^{-1},$$

$$\begin{aligned} B &= HA, \\ C &= QA^{-T}H^T R^{-1}, \\ D &= A. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Thus, it is known [10] that the prediction error covariance tends to the steady state prediction error covariance and that the convergence is independent of the initial uncertainty, that is, independent of the value of the initial condition P_0 . Thus, we are able to assume zero initial condition $P_0=0$ and so we are to use the initial condition $K_0=0$. It is clear that K_k tends to a steady state value \tilde{K} satisfying $\tilde{K} = (C + D\tilde{K})[L + B\tilde{K}]^{-1}$. Based on expressions (9), we are able to derive the following nonlinear iterative equation with respect to the Kalman filter gain K_k : $K_{k+1} = (C + DK_k)[L + BK_k]^{-1} = c + l[K_k^{-1} + b]^{-1}d$, where L, B, C, D are given by (10) and $l = D - CL^{-1}B, b = L^{-1}B, c = CL^{-1}, d = L^{-1}, K_0 = P_0H^T[HP_0H^T + R]^{-1}$.

It is known [7-10] that the prediction error covariance tends to the steady state prediction error covariance and that the convergence is independent of the initial uncertainty, that is, independent of the value of the initial condition P_0 .

This algorithm for the computation of the steady state Kalman filter gain \tilde{K} . It is clear that the direct computation of the Kalman filter gain is feasible only if the following restriction holds: $n=m$. The advantage of the presented algorithms is the autonomous computation of the steady state Kalman filter gain. Especially, the steady state Kalman filter gain is important, when we want to compute the parameters of the steady state Kalman filter

$$x_{k+1/k+1} = (I - \tilde{K}H)Ax_{k/k} + \tilde{K}z_{k+1} = (I - \tilde{G})Ax_{k/k} + \tilde{K}z_{k+1}. \quad (11)$$

It is obvious from (11) that the parameters of the steady state Kalman filter are related to the steady state Kalman filter gain.

In particular, the steady state prediction error covariance can be computed via the steady state gain and is given by

$$\tilde{P}_p = [I - \tilde{K}H]^{-1} \tilde{K}RH[H^T H]^{-1}. \quad (12)$$

Indeed, from (2), arises $\tilde{K} = \tilde{P}_p H^T [H\tilde{P}_p H^T + R]^{-1}$, which leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{K}(H\tilde{P}_p H^T + R) &= \tilde{P}_p H^T \Rightarrow \tilde{K}H\tilde{P}_p H^T + \tilde{K}R = \tilde{P}_p H^T \\ \Rightarrow \tilde{P}_p H^T - \tilde{K}H\tilde{P}_p H^T &= \tilde{K}R \Rightarrow (I - \tilde{K}H)\tilde{P}_p H^T = \tilde{K}R \\ \Rightarrow \tilde{P}_p H^T &= [I - \tilde{K}H]^{-1} \tilde{K}R \Rightarrow \tilde{P}_p H^T H = [I - \tilde{K}H]^{-1} \tilde{K}RH. \end{aligned}$$

Since $rank(H) = n$, the matrix $H^T H$ is nonsingular [12]; thus from the last equation arises immediately the formula of the steady state prediction error covariance in (12).

From here, by (3), the steady state estimation error covariance can be computed via the steady state prediction error covariance $\tilde{P}_e = [I - \tilde{K}H]\tilde{P}_p$.

Based on the above, we can say, the Kalman filter gain arises in Kalman filter equations in linear estimation and is associated with linear systems. The gain is a matrix through which the estimation and the prediction of the state as well as the corresponding estimation and prediction error covariance matrices are computed. Thus, if we talk about modeling, these Kalman filtering expressions for a linear discrete system and the actual filtering process is the current process for predicting and correcting recursive and iterative nature [13-15]. This does not require storing large amounts of data. When new data is received, the new filtering value can be calculated at any time.

This stable iterative algorithm for estimating elements of the matrix gain of the Kalman filter allows stabilizing the synthesis of the dynamic object control system.

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